

Organizing Physical Education and Health Events through Sports Clubs

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Abstract:

In the article, proper adherence to a healthy lifestyle, proper organization of nutrition, organization of an active lifestyle, organization of day and work regime based on biological regimes, maintenance of mental peace or nervous balance, alcoholism, abstinence from harmful habits such as drunkenness, drug addiction, observance of neatness and decency, attitude to the environment, physical education and sports, and issues related to health clubs are expressed.

Keywords: physical training and sports coaches, activities of sports clubs, healthy lifestyle.

HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

In recent years, it has become clear that the only way to preserve and strengthen people's health and live a long life is a healthy lifestyle. Therefore, people in developed countries try to make their lifestyle more healthy. The advantage of this is that a person first of all saves money spent on treatment of diseases. Secondly, while ensuring his health, he also strengthens his economy. The laws of the market economy are healthy. It requires strength.

Proponents of a healthy lifestyle claim that if people follow the following lifestyles, they will almost never get sick. For this, it is necessary to pay attention to the following in marriage, or rather, to be educated in these matters.

- Proper organization of meals.
- This means organizing the food we eat on a daily basis based on the physiological and biological requirements of the human body. Proper nutrition should be organized in such a way that it does not burden the human body with its physical, chemical and biological properties, and on the contrary, it should be able to quickly and easily digest and provide the necessary nutrients for the body.

- Organization of active life.
- That is, if a person takes more physical training exercises, sports games, and body-training procedures in his daily life, it will accelerate physiological and biological processes in the body, and as a result, a person's mood and work performance will improve. Undoubtedly, this condition serves to strengthen health. Kun va ish rejimini biologik rejimlar asosida tashkil qilish.

It is known that in the whole universe and in nature, events are repeated based on a certain order. For example, the rising and setting of the sun at certain times every day, and the repeating of the year at certain times, are clear examples of the fact that actions in nature are subject to a certain order. Similarly, orderly movements occur in the human body. For example, heart beats 70-75 times per minute and breathing repeats 12-16 times per minute, indicating that there is a certain regularity in the human body. There are more than 100 such regulated biological phenomena in the human body. Changes in the tissues of the human body are also subject to this law. So, since the phenomena in nature and our body are subject to certain laws, we should organize our daily life based on a certain order, and this order must be compatible with the changes in nature and our body. For example: since the beginning of mankind, the activity in his body has learned to increase during the day and decrease at night.

Providing mental peace or nervous balance.

- The essence of this condition is great. Because the normalization of our body and internal organs determines our mental state and mood. Therefore, it is important to think well, to think well, to abstain from bad and sinful actions, to not give way to lust and Satan, to listen carefully to the teachings of our forefathers, and to apply all this in life. 'I, being courteous, all these serve to preserve and strengthen health.
- **Abstaining from harmful habits** (drinking, gambling, drug addiction). There is a lot of talk about their harm to the human body, health, and marriage. In our opinion, it can be said that a person who does not know the harm of these habits does not exist. Such people can be called people who are indifferent to their health, who live at risk and do not think about their health, who live only for the pleasure of this day, one-time deceptive entertainment.
- **The issue of observing freedom and mediocrity, attitude to the environment.** Human activity is undoubtedly associated with a certain degree of influence on one's body and the environment. For example, after doing something, hands and clothes get dirty. The skin is polluted by the waste products produced by the body and internal organs. Food and other things that are necessary for our life produce waste. Throwing these in the right place will pollute the environment. As a result, there is a situation in water, soil, and air that has a negative impact on human health. That is why keeping neat and tidy is one of the most important requirements of our daily life.

ORGANIZING HEALTH EVENTS

Our future is in the hands of healthy and well-rounded, spiritually mature young people. Therefore, physical education and sports activities are widely used among young people. In the future, great attention will be paid to physical education and sports rehabilitation activities along with professional training with students of vocational colleges and higher educational institutions who will become mature specialists.

The purpose of physical education and sports health activities is to teach students the requirements of physical development of the body and a healthy lifestyle. At the same time, physical education, sports and wellness events will greatly help to master professional training.

Physical education activities for students are in the form of morning physical education, physical education classes, sports club training, sports fitness competitions and holidays. Morning physical education classes are held in public in student dormitories, independently in residences and families.

Morning physical training can consist of exercises for arms, legs and body muscles, breathing exercises. Physical education classes are organized according to the student curriculum.

In physical education classes, students are trained in football, basketball, volleyball, and handball techniques. Also, athletics, gymnastics, wrestling and push sports movements are taught.

Sports holidays and competitions on the agenda can include tourist walks, receiving water treatments, swimming and bathing classes, competitions and competitions between groups. During the training of the sports clubs, the students gain specialization in sports. Students demonstrate their physical, technical and tactical training in competitions.

Medical supervision is of great importance in the organization of physical training and sports rehabilitation activities with students in sports clubs. All students included in healthy groups are involved in sports health activities. Preparatory and remedial physical education classes are conducted with special group students.

Effective organization of physical education events with students in sports clubs is the main factor in their becoming mature specialists.

The issue of organizing physical training events with students in sports clubs was studied in the graduation thesis. Physical education activities conducted with students are morning physical education, exercises in sports clubs, sports competitions and holidays, and physical education classes.

When students are involved in physical education activities, their physical development and health are studied under medical supervision. As a result of medical supervision, plans for students to engage in physical exercises are developed. Infirm and sick students are engaged in therapeutic physical exercises. Physical education classes are aimed at physical development of students and formation of professional physical training skills and abilities. Lessons can include sports and action games, gymnastics, athletics, wrestling and swimming.

Morning physical education exercises prepare students for the educational process and make them healthy. Morning physical education classes should be organized independently in student houses and residences.

Sports club training helps students master the movements and exercises of sports and become physically fit. As a means of health and training, tourism and hiking tours are organized with students. During these trainings, the resistance level of the student's body to diseases will increase with the help of natural factors.

Students should carry out physical education processes in the form of practical professional physical training events. This ensures that students will become mature specialists and physically fit, experienced personnel in the future.

And finally, another important condition for a healthy lifestyle: making friends with healthy people. Because you will be healthy only if your friends are healthy people. And we wish you to follow the path of health.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sportni yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ 3031-sonli Qarori.-Toshkent, 2017-yil 3-iyun.

2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2018-yil 5-martdagi “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida jismoniy tarbiya va sport sohasida davlat boshqaruvi tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi Farmoni.
3. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 20-apreldagi “Oliy ta’lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-2909-sonli qarori.
4. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 27-iyuldagi “Oliy ma’lumotli mutaxassislar tayyorlash sifatini oshirishda iqtisodiyot sohalari va tarmoqlarining ishtirokini yanada kengaytirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi PQ-3151-sonli qarori.
5. Mirziyoev Sh.M. Tanqidiy tahlil, qat’iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik-har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik qoidasi bo‘lishi kerak.-Toshkent:O‘zbekiston, 2017.-104 b.
6. Usmonxo‘jayev T., Xo‘jayev F. Harakatli o‘yinlar.-T.: O‘qituvchi, 1992.-182 b.
7. Usmonxo‘jayev T., Xo‘jayev F. 1001 o‘yin.-T.:Ibn Sino nomidagi nashriyot, 1990.-352.
8. Xurramov E.E. Jismoniy tarbiya o‘qituvchilarining innovatsion faoliyatini tashkil qilish mexanizmlari.-Toshkent:Fan va texnologiyalar, 2018.-144 b.
9. Frolov V. Sayrda jismoniy tarbiya mashg‘ulotlari, o‘yinlari va mashqlari.-T.: O‘qituvchi, 1990.-176.